

DAISY
LET'S TURN ON TRANSFORMATION

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ANNEX A: TRANSFORMATIVE DIAGNOSTIC TOOL (TRD2)

Core definitions and full list of questions

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Core definitions:

E. Equity

Innovations have implications for justice, fairness, equity. We refer to these concepts collectively as equity. There are different typologies and conceptualisations of equity, with broadly discussed categories being procedural, distributive, and recognitional, and some discussions highlighting restorative, capabilities, epistemic types of equity (EEA 2024). As we focus on creating a tool that allows diagnostic reflection of the current and future potential and for use by a broader audiences, we focus on procedural (including epistemic), distributive, recognitional (including restorative), and capabilities types of equity (building on Langemeyer & Connolly, 2020; Wijsman & Berbés-Blázquez, 2022).

EP. Procedural equity

Procedural equity means that everyone has a fair chance to take part in decisions that affect them and procedures are transparent. It means being informed, having access to the process, and being treated fairly when decisions are made. People should be able to speak up, ask questions, and influence what happens. Procedural equity aims to fix systems where some voices are excluded, ignored, or undervalued, including by ensuring those that are systematically marginalised have access to procedures and knowledge co-creation (epistemic equity). When processes are fair, decisions are more inclusive and more trusted (building on Langemeyer & Connolly, 2020; Wijsman & Berbés-Blázquez, 2022).

ED. Distributive equity

Distributive equity means that benefits and burdens are shared fairly across different groups. It looks at who gains and who loses from policies, projects, or changes. Some people might get improved access and benefits from the use of biodiversity, while others bear the costs. Distributive equity focuses on changing this, so that no specific actor is systematically left with

more harm and fewer benefits (building on Langemeyer & Connolly, 2020; Biermann & Kalfagianni, 2020; Wijsman & Berbés-Blázquez, 2022).

ER. Recognition equity

Recognition equity means that people's identities, experiences, and values are respected. It means listening to different cultural perspectives, languages, and histories, as well as recognising historical backgrounds, including historical injustices (restorative equity), when making decisions. Some groups are often overlooked or treated as less important. This can lead to exclusion and unfair treatment. Recognition equity works to make sure that all voices count, that differences are valued, and that no one is made to feel invisible (building on Wijsman & Berbés-Blázquez, 2022).

EC. Capabilities equity

Capabilities equity means that people have real opportunities to live the kind of life they value. It is not just about having access to resources, but being able to use them meaningfully, that is to flourish—such as for staying healthy, feeling safe, and making choices that matter. Biodiversity-related or social challenges can block these chances, especially for already disadvantaged groups. Capabilities equity is based on trust and focuses on removing the barriers so that everyone has the support they need to thrive (building on Sen, 1999; Nussbaum, 2011).

B. Biodiversity

Biodiversity means the variety of life on earth, including differences within species, between species, habitats and across ecosystems. Biodiversity contributes to healthy ecosystem services that support for instance, essential services like food, clean water, and climate regulation. Pro-biodiversity decisions involve improving the state of nature, avoiding risks that lead to its decline, and restoring what has been lost (IPBES, n.d.).

BG. Genetic biodiversity

Genetic diversity refers to the variety of genes within a species. It enables species to adapt to changing environments, resist diseases, and maintain healthy populations. Preserving genetic diversity is crucial for food security and resilience to climate change (IPBES, n.d.).

BS. Species biodiversity

Species diversity refers to the variety of different species in a given area. It includes both the number of species and their relative abundance. High species diversity contributes to ecosystem productivity and stability (IPBES, n.d.).

BH. Habitat diversity

Habitat diversity refers to the variety of natural environments where species live, such as forests, wetlands, and grasslands. Diverse habitats support a wide range of species and ecological processes. Protecting and restoring habitats is essential for conserving biodiversity (IPBES, n.d.).

BE. Ecosystem diversity

Ecosystem diversity refers to the variety of ecosystems in a region, encompassing the different communities of organisms and their physical environments. Diverse ecosystems provide a range of services vital for human well-being and environmental health (IPBES, n.d.).

Transformations

Innovations can trigger social transformations. Transformation is a system-wide social change, meaning a process that leads to substantially new forms of social views, practices and structures. Such social transformations can be at the personal, practical, and political levels (IPBES, 2024; O'Brien, 2018).

Transformations at the personal level

Transformations at the personal level mean that individuals who are exposed to innovation might revisit and adjust their views, attitudes, perceptions towards the social-environmental issues this particular innovation addresses. As a result of (desired) transformation towards

certain issue, individuals might become much more aware, substantially improve their understanding, and integrate their new views in their decision-making. As a result of such desired transformation, they might generally care more about the issue, they might value what happens to the topic more, they might believe it is more important than before, and they might have stronger emotional reactions (building on IPBES 2024 and O'Brien, 2018).

Transformations at the practical level

Transformations at the practical level mean change in specific actions, interventions, strategies and behaviours that directly contribute to a (desired) outcome related to social-environmental challenges. For example, these might include more solar installations, reduced meat consumption, upgraded infrastructure, new educational tools, promotion of bicycle riding, construction of sea walls, and so on (building on IPBES 2024 and O'Brien, 2018).

Transformations at the political level

Transformations at the political level mean change in systems and structures that facilitate or constrain practical responses to various social-environmental challenges. Systems can be described as relationships between parts that form a larger whole, and structures describe the norms, rules, regulations, institutions, regimes and incentives that influence how systems are designed, organised and governed. Systems and structures are often created, codified and managed through political processes (building on O'Brien, 2018; Schatzki, 2023).

TRD2 questions – Current and Future dimensions

List of questions including both the current context and a future-oriented perspective (with 2050 as a reference year, following the target suggested by IPBES, 2024).

This worksheet includes a set of questions designed to assess the equity, biodiversity, and transformation potential of innovations. Each question invites your assessment of the current situation and your estimation of what could realistically change by 2050. Please rate each dimension on a scale from 0 (not at all) to 4 (very much), or select 'don't know' if you're unsure.

Table A1. List of questions for biodiversity dimension of TRD2. Scoring legend: from 0 very low to 100 very high

Question	Current context (now) (if you think about the current context of this innovation...)	Future potential (2050) (if you think about what could realistically change by 2050...)	Comment if any
Biodiversity - ecosystem			
BE1 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to improve biodiversity in terms of ecosystems diversity?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
BE2 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to contribute to restoration of ecosystems?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
BE3 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to reduce the risk of ecosystems loss?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
Biodiversity – genetic			

BG1 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to improve biodiversity in terms of genetic diversity?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
BG2 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to reduce the loss of biodiversity in terms of genetic diversity?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
BG3 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to restore lost genetic diversity?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
Biodiversity – habitat			
BH1 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to improve biodiversity in terms of habitats diversity?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
BH2 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to reduce the risk of habitat loss?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
BH3 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to improve the restoration of habitats?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
Biodiversity – species			
BS1 – to what extent does this innovation	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	

have the potential to improve biodiversity in terms of species diversity?			
BS2 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to reduce the risk of species extinction?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
BS3 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to recover species lost in specific areas?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	

Table A2. List of questions for equity dimension of TRD2. Scoring legend: from 0 very low to 100 very high

Question	Current context (now) (if you think about the current context of this innovation...)	Future potential (2050) (if you think about what could realistically change by 2050...)	Comment (if any)
Equity – capabilities			
EC1 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to improve the actual capabilities of people to respond to challenges (e.g., skills, access to tools, empowerment, mobility)?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
EC2 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to avoid the risk of reinforcing capability	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	

gaps or unequal opportunities?			
EC3 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to enhance environmental and social well-being by building capacity, resilience, and long-term sustainability?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
Equity – distributive			
ED1 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to improve the fair distribution of environmental benefits (e.g., access to clean water, air, green spaces)?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
ED2 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to avoid the risk of reinforcing existing environmental inequalities (e.g., pollution burdens, biodiversity loss affecting certain groups)?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
ED3 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to restore fairness in the distribution of environmental resources for	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	

historically disadvantaged populations (e.g., low-income or colonised communities)?			
Equity – procedural			
EP1 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to improve inclusivity and participation in decision-making for marginalised communities (e.g., racialised, indigenous, or low-income groups)?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
EP2 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to avoid the risk of exclusion from decision-making processes, especially for vulnerable or excluded groups?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
EP3 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to restore trust and legitimacy in governance and institutional processes for affected communities?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
Equity – recognition			
ER1 – to what extent does this innovation	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	

have the potential to recognise and respect diverse cultural, social, and other knowledge systems?			
ER2 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to address patterns of misrecognition or marginalisation that contribute to environmental injustice?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
ER3 – to what extent does this innovation have the potential to promote dignity, visibility, and voice for historically excluded communities?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	

Table A3. List of questions for TRANSFORMATION dimension of TRD2. Scoring legend: from 0 very low to 100 very high

Question	Current context (now) (if you think about the current context of this innovation...)	Future potential (2050) (if you think about what could realistically change by 2050...)	Comments (if any)
Transformation – personal			
TPE1 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the personal level by	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	

improving substantially awareness?			
TPE2 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the personal level by creating substantially stronger views, attitudes, opinions?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
TPE3 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the personal level by triggering emotions?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
Transformation – practical			
TPR1 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the practical level by enabling new actions, interventions, or strategies?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	
TPR2 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the practical level by changing day-to-day behaviours or habits related to sustainability?	[0 ...100]	[0 ...100]	

<p>TPR3 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the practical level by supporting the development or spread of sustainable infrastructure, technologies, or services?</p>	<p>[0 ...100]</p>	<p>[0 ...100]</p>	
<p>Transformation – political</p>			
<p>TPO1 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the political level by changing how systems are organized or coordinated to address environmental and social challenges?</p>	<p>[0 ...100]</p>	<p>[0 ...100]</p>	
<p>TPO2 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the political level by influencing rules, norms, or institutions relevant to sustainability?</p>	<p>[0 ...100]</p>	<p>[0 ...100]</p>	
<p>TPO3 – to the best of your knowledge, what is the potential of this innovation to trigger transformations at the</p>	<p>[0 ...100]</p>	<p>[0 ...100]</p>	

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political level by shaping policies, incentives, or governance processes?			
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ILLUSTRATION OF THE TOOL:

Figure A1. Illustration of TRD2 output.